

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT PRACTICES: ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SMES OF THE FOOD MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to analyze and explain the impact of CRM practices on organizational performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in the Food Manufacturing Industry. This conceptual review focuses on the literature evidence showing positive or negative correlations between organizational performance and context factors chosen in the CRM strategy and implementation model. The proposed model integrates elements that have already been integrated into the literature review on CRM model and implementation as there was also a need to choose elements carefully to adapt and recreate CRM strategy and implementation model for this research paper.

Organizational performance of the CRM strategy and implementation model was used to support and argue with the literature review on key elements, such as Business Development, Customer Retention, Customer Acquisition Strategies, and Concerning also with techniques, systems, and technologies building loyalty and ways of attracting new consumers despite of those already there. This paper offers the SMEs of the food manufacturing industry clear guidelines for how the CRM strategy and implementation model by using the Evolution of CRM readiness, CRM project management strategy, Strategy development process, Value creation process, Multi-channel integration process, Performance assessment process, CRM change management strategy, Data repository (warehouse), Employee Engagement process can impact and be used to facilitate and improve organizational performance and result in positive outcomes that will help SME of food manufacturing industry achieve a competitive advantage.

Keywords:

Organizational Performance, Small and Medium Enterprises, Business Development, Customer Retention, Customer Acquisition Strategies, Technology

1. Literature Review

This paper explains the theoretical literature review on topic of the Customer Relationship Management Practices: Organizational Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises of the Food Manufacturing Industry. Over the years Customer Relationship Management, also known as CRM, has suffered many attempts to be defined or studied as a mechanism that supports the transformation of companies to better-implemented strategies, practices, and technologies intending to gain and retain customers in a profitable way. As an organizational mechanism within any company, CRM aims to transform a short-term operational model with the customers into a long-term relationship model based on adjacent customer information obtained through channels and points of contact.

(Visser, 2019) States that although CRM is contested by various information technology (IT) vendors, consultants, and academics, information technology companies use the term CRM to describe software applications that assists sector of the company such as marketing, selling, and service functions of businesses. Besides, with all the problems found in this modern business era, companies have decided to use CRM as a priority for their marketing strategy and the customer as a central member of all their marketing actions demonstrated. Regardless of the size of any organization, companies have been spending billions of dollars each year on CRM systems or applications, however, it is believed that the results in some cases are not positive considering that 70% of these CRM projects result in losses and do not present any type of performance for companies, hence there is an urgent need to study and analyze

how CRM presents itself to companies and why companies are unable to present effective productivity to stop insignificant resolution problems using the same mechanism (Mohamad, 2014). In addition, there are issues that make it difficult to implement or integrate CRM system management within an industry. According to (Reinartz, 2004) these issues are based on the lack of financial resources and the lack of knowledge to work with the CRM system or because the same tool is also predominantly aimed at customers rather than Small and Medium Enterprises of Food Manufacturers. He also argues that its implementation within an organization as a corporate strategy adds long-term growth sustainability compared to other organizations that don't share the same idea. (Chen, 2003) States that many studies characterize the failure of the CRM tool as the money spent by the company's executive.

(Da Silva Pinto, 2020) Argues that it goes beyond that, as the company's executive needs the strategic support of several leaders within the company to implement CRM and thus improve business values and obtain a competitive advantage over the competition. Overall, it will be important that all cooperation departments are familiar with the customer and focus on retaining as much information as possible in terms of preferences; how many times they called, complaints made, money spent per month or year, and their suggestions regarding the product purchased. Second, it necessarily focuses on the concept of CRM.

(Maria, 2019) Claims that the business as seen from the customer's point of view and the economic and financial factors are preponderant in corporate environments. He also emphasizes in his research that benchmarking with competitors or companies from other segments can be interesting in breaking paradigms. From the outset, the concept of marketing has been related to CRM by many researchers, some of whom would describe Customer Relationship Management as Customer Relationship Marketing. Moreover, the marketing concept paved the way for the customer-centric concept and its organization is based on a culture of beliefs and values focused on the customers because it makes the customer the center of the company's strategic and operational thinking.

(Costa, 2020) States that it is necessary for the executive and other members of the company's board to comply with the business decisions made, so as not to put customer relationship efforts ahead of other aspects of the business, as if it were a single activity restricted exclusively to sales and marketing, which is why formalized CRM planning is necessary and not acting impulsively by looking at the competition. It should also be noted that identifying who will sponsor and lead CRM within an organization is important because management carried out by an element that does not have the capacity to provoke and sustain changes within the organization is the same thing as nothing. In addition, the reason why the participation of all sectors of the organization was highlighted is that CRM is not a static tool, as it may or may not evolve depending on the different relationship focus that each cooperation. Apart from that, as technology advances, there is a great need to respond to an increasingly competitive global market and it is becoming clear that companies have and will have to adopt a more centralized information collection system, believing that the individual customer is the central unit of analysis and action, with an ability to don't allow the consumer to look at competitor and be repetitive buyer, thus passing the definition of customer-centric and customer retention. In fact, considering that customer retention in CRM is crucial for food manufacturers due to the organization's limited resources, CRM practices can add value to the customer while retention will build a better relationship. Besides, this type of customer relationship can bring a competitive advantage to the organization, it comes easier to adapt to the CRM model created by the organization based on cultural, operational, and technological characteristics. (Espinosa-Gracia, 2023) States that there are external factors such environmental factors that play a role in a company's CRM performance and these factors also can cause a paradigm shift in the business.

(Payne A. &, 2005) Claims that CRM had and has been more successful in the service sector than in the manufacturing sector. He goes on to say that the time has come to introduce changes related to the implementation of CRM as its performance should be beneficial to more industries and different sectors.

This article tries to articulate the problems of the food manufacturing industry, because after much research is believed that it needs a CRM solution to phase the entire business model and the entire information technology structure in order to create sustainable growth. This study identified business issues to:

1. Understand the full range of effects of marketing intelligence and customer relationship management (CRM) in maintaining long term relationships with current consumers and building relationships with new consumers.
2. Understand the impact of information and communication technologies (ICT) on customers relationship (Internal and external) and knowledge management.

3. Understand the look over on how artificial intelligence, automation, analytics, the AI reality software can bring innovation with customers relationship.

In order to provide insights and outline CRM solutions for the SME food manufacturing industry. This study will discuss theoretical and managerial issues with suggestions focused on the evolution of CRM in the industry.

2. Organizational Performance in SME of Food Manufacturing Industry

Many researchers focus their attention on market orientation and company performance in the manufacturing and service industries, but unfortunately, studies carried out in SME food manufacturing are scarce. However, organizational performance is defined as achieving goals in a state of constant change and its objective is optimizing results.

(Aziz, 2010) Indicates that the perception of demand can change at any time based on the information provided by the market, so low demand harms the level of production of goods or desired products and the opposite happens when demand is high. He also suggests that this disparity is controllable if Small and Medium Enterprises in the food manufacturing industry opt for a market and performance orientation using additional variables such as market turbulence, technology, and competitive intensity.

(Gholami, 2013) Emphasizes in his results about the structural equation model that knowledge management incorporates knowledge acquisition, knowledge storage, knowledge creation, knowledge sharing, knowledge implementation, and organizational performance including critical elements such as productivity, financial performance, staff performance, innovation, work relationship, and customer satisfaction. He concludes that after running a model was found that all the variables are statistically significant with the independent variables such as organizational performance and knowledge management, as knowledge management practices in Small and Medium Enterprises positively influenced organizational performance.

(Mbugi, 2022) Analyzing the food and beverage production market in Tanzania, he states that poor inventory control harms industrial competitiveness. He highlights that there is a very strong link between inventory control management and organizational performance, the reason that led him to write this was the analysis of the research carried out at Economic Order Quantity that identifies how important inventory control is, and its benefits for economic production, quantity and quality of products in the context of costs projected and accounted for certain deadlines for customers, leading to maximum profitability.

(Atnafu, 2018) Mentions in his research paper Empirical Evidence from Micro and Small Enterprises in Ethiopia that inventory control management is effective and credible for a company especially when it offers high-quality products with the unique advantages of premium changing, thus increasing the profit margin of sales and return on investment.

3. Customer Relationship Management

Among many definitions, a CRM is a tool that work close with a company and managers into planning, organizing, interacting, measuring and developing people or enterprises. Perhaps anybody who changes in principles depending on who is dealing that's not a man who can lead an organization. Because management goes beyond commanding people, actually it is a function rather than power, in other words, it is a responsibility for contribution. (Rangone, 2002) Claims that there are three types of group management, in the first scenario there will be the traditional managerial function and responsibility for the work of others. He also claims that in the second part, there will be others who don't exercise this responsibility within their specific mission, and there will be the final group that incorporates something ambiguous and in-between: people whose job is that of team leader or task force captain, or people who combine the role of advisor to senior management with the responsibility of supervising and managing a workforce in a particular area. Therefore, it is necessary for marketing to be the starting point for CRM implementation within any organization due to the technological advancement that has impacted the CRM program in a way that significant changes in its creation, development, and implementation have begun to be seen. Most of those changes will automatically reflect more on Knowledge Management (KM) which is the process of identifying, organizing, storing and disseminating information within an organization. Conversely, the lack of knowledge within an organization can be costly to a business, just as can be arduous to understand Knowledge Management Systems (KMS), which helps to lead the organization to a better operational efficiencies.

(Peter, 2011) States that in terms of management, most managers spend most of their time on things that are not 'managing'. He also argues that any position inside any company should be given distinctly, meaning that every manager should have one position and one responsibility. Typically, institutions differ based on a specific purpose, mission, and social function. But in the enterprise, all these combinations will reflect on the economic performance that the company will have over the years, as a mission.

(Drucker, 1977) States that like any other business, there are two sides to the coin, the first is characterizes by the size of the company, that is, the larger the company, the more management and decision-making problems it will have, and the smaller the business, the less talented people, the less qualified the workers and the less marketing skills it will have. Continuously, he says that decision-making is an essential element of business activity and can be done rationally, moreover, the non-rational element is seen in a traditional form of management that is differentiated between "decision" and "decision", also "we don't talk about a "decision" that two and two make four; we call it the right answer". In other words, the author emphasizes that in the modern era, we talk about decisions when, in fact, there is only one right answer. Unlike many decisions in the company, entrepreneurial decisions do not imply a formula or the right decision, but rather a high level that all entrepreneurs need which is the ability to inovative and change the trend of the business. In any case, it is more coherent than following and anticipating decisions within a company, because an entrepreneur with rigor and a disciplined mind can distinguish a critical decision from an entrepreneurial one, as long as the aim is to eliminate risk and minimize it. It is important to differentiate decisions within a company due to the relationships maintained with different customers. However, it is known that every investment made to build a company requires a return on investment, but when the return is immediate it makes an expected long-term relationship with customers difficult, the same way it makes the company's business strategies and models difficult. A company with a well-oriented marketing and communication strategy makes it possible to identify itself within two very important market categories, B2B and B2C. Since these categories are in accordance with each company's business strategies, the choice of customers, whether corporate or mass, will decide how to market the products or services. However, B2B referes to "Business to Business", that is, the corporate or industrial market, while B2C referes to "Business to Consumer", that is, the mass consumer or final consumer market, in this case, companies that offer products or services to people. (Caldari, 2007) Claims that the last of the great English classical economics, Alfred Marshall added that production factors such as; production, land, labor, and capital are part of management. (Ostrovitianov, 1972) States in his scientific work that, in a socialist system, the organization of society plays an important role in the enjoyment of the wealth created by collective work and that belongs to all the workers. He goes on to say that in a capitalist system, production is done for the sake of production if profit is sough as the ultimate goal, workers are interested above all in securing the conditions that will enable them to stop working compulsorily for their exploiters and start working for themselves and using all the achievements of technology, science, and culture to this end.

(Murakami, 1996) Claims in his book that there is a collision of values and visions between industrialism and anti-industrialism and these can be seen in two ways, the first is summarized for those who see the limits of science and technology in the profound ethical and medical issues raised by continued industrialization and the environmental movement, the second is based on conflicts of interest for two types of political economy, those that are in principle pro-orientation classic liberal economic growth, and those that adopt "developmentalism" in which the government plays crucial roles in promoting economic growth.

3.1 Dimension of CRM

The definition of CRM incorporates processes and technologies for managing customer relationships. It is with this technology that Small and Medium Enterprises must create a strategic commitment. There are two dimensions of CRM technology that Small and Medium Enterprises should take advantage of. Firstly, applications are made for customers with the intention of ensuring a better relationship with agents, systems, or websites. On the other hand, there are business-oriented applications that cover sales force automation, marketing automation, and customer service and support. The use of projects by Small and Medium Businesses for their customers makes the use of both dimensions important. However, the technological dimension of CRM includes information technology (IT), databases, customer data, data warehouses, database marketing, data mining, call centers, and Sales Force Automation (SFA). As a point of business strategy for selecting and managing customers in the short and long term, there are three segments in which CRM is present: Operational, analytical and collaborative.

3.1.1 CRM Operational - Sales force Automation

Due to the business changes that many companies have made the improvement of their practices and procedures provides for the allocation of critical information with their suppliers distributors, and customers. However, Enterprise Resource Planning style tools enable interaction with customers at various levels from order management, billing and collection to marketing and sales automation and management.

According to (Da Silva, 2020) Enterprise Resource Planning offers a different business vision when integrated with CRM. He continues by saying that Enterprise Resource Planning has applications such as ASAP and PeopleSoft that can take care of real-time business processes such as production, order processing, and inventory management.

According to (Murta, 2017) the integration of these two elements creates a failure or problems in the implementation of operational CRM in companies.

3.1.2 CRM Analytical – Business Intelligence

After a comprehensive overview of the operating system and its functionality, the analytical CRM makes use of the applications and all the customer data collected by the operational CRM. Analytical CRM plays a key role in gathering information using the applications created in operational CRM to help the company implement beneficial corporate systems by analyzing the data obtained and generated. Nevertheless, the use of applications created in operational CRM also facilitates the provision of credible information and reports aids decision-making and improves company performance.

3.1.3 CRM Collaborative – Social CRM

From a bottom-up perspective, analytical CRM focuses on data mining and customer intelligence for strategic or tactical purposes.

In a more specific sense, it is a communication and coordination network that aims to open up the pathways between customers and through various channels. Since the early nineties, there has been a rise in performance between manufacturers and retailers thanks to the concept of Efficient Consumer Response (ECR). Since the early nineties, there has been a rise in performance among manufacturers and retailers thanks to the concept of Efficient Consumer Response and its implication to two important areas such as marketing and logistics.

(Kracklauer, 2004) States that the ECR implementation in the consumer goods market was first carried out in logistics because its potential facilitates cost reduction and is easy to obtain. He also states that the term collaborative customer relationship management means that identifying, attracting, acquiring, and developing profitable target customers for bilateral sales and profit growth now plays a role in the consumer goods market that must be recognized at a cooperative level.

3.2 Evolution of Customer Relationship Management

Customer relationship management began in the early 1950s. The main objective was to track customer transactions and build strategies to maintain and develop customer relationships through personalization. The evolution of CRM brings with it different eras of transformation or evolution. It all started in the 1950s when the Rolodex was the main CRM tool. Over time there was a need for CRM to develop and grow, so in the 1970s the mainframe or computers were created to register the customer information in database marketing. In 1980, database marketing was created for all companies interested in this tool.

(Dyche, 2002) States that the tool was created for all companies interested. He also states that the tool was useful but presented a source of problems in organizing customer data, so in the same year contact management software was created based on the idea of introducing the PC, which led companies to collect and organize more customer data. At the same time, the development of the digital version of Rolodezi, aimed at contact management created opportunities for one-way relationships with customers. This was also the beginning of sales calls in which active sales agents called customers to make direct sales as shown in the Table I. Table I presents an idea of how CRM can help the organizational performance of an SME in the food industry. Thus, this can be achieved by utilizing industry benefits for customer data across the organization and industry benefits by applying innovative CRM technology across the organization. However, in the perspective of CRM evolution the year 1990 has seen little change, with marketing adding new features such as tracking and analyzing customer data while automating other tasks.

(Uwe, 2021) States that Tom Siebel left Oracle and founded Siebel Systems in 1993, becoming the most popular SFA vendor at the time. In fact, the term CRM was born with the development of Sales Force Automation (SFA), which had an enormous capacity for converting leads and optimizing marketing campaigns presented in the Table I. The launch of the first mobile CRM called Siebel Sales Handled in 1990 and 1999 by Siebel System encouraged Salesforce to offer the first cloud-based SaaS CRM system to the market Microsoft Dynamics became a major player in the CRM industry in the 2000s as demonstrated in the Table 1. The same year was marked by the creation of the internet bubble and in 2004 SugarCRM introduced open source CRM systems with all this growth and development in 2007 cloud-based CRM was created with the aim of developing applications to allow companies to customize their web-based CRM as shown in the Table 1. Ideologically, this program involved the most prestigious companies at the time. The rise of social networks in 2000 led to the creation of social CRM, which over time underwent a major technological shift from transactional CRM to interactive CRM as shown in the Table 1. (Payne A. &, 2016) states that this phase took many companies closer to what we now call the technological future with applications centered on customer interactions and the automation of social networks and customer service. On the other hand, in 2010s with the introduction of new integration capabilities, CRM systems gained improvements in data analytics, reporting, mobile access, AI, and machine learning, thus CRM systems could increase their integrations with business intelligence services and communication services as shown in the Table I. Nowadays, with CRM transitions to Cx, CRM strategy moves from a focus on marketing, sales, and services to focus on increasing sales and how the business can use that data to personalize the customer experience shown in the Figure 2.

Table 1: CRM’s advantages for industry

Industry Benefits for Customer Data Sharing	Industry Benefits Applying CRM Innovative Technology
Top levels of customer satisfaction	It extends self-service and internet applications for customers
Advantages for cross-selling and direct Sales	Attracts new and existing customers through personalized communications and better targeting
Broad data on customer trends and preferences	Integrates customer and supplier relations
Complete and integrated view of the customer	Build metrics to analyze common and unique customer patterns
Optimization and targeting of segments and individual customers	
Efficient call/service centers	

Source: Adapted from (Chen, 2003)

Although, Cx strategy focuses on using a complete view of customer data to anticipate the customer’s needs and personalize experiences so that people become loyal customers, Table I presents the benefits of applying CRM in the industry, it is important to bear in mind that these benefits are likely to be accompanied by risks. Just as the benefits were characterized in Table 1, the risks can be seen from the perspective of project failure, insufficient return on investment, non-planned budget revisions, unsatisfied clients, loss of confidence from customers, and detour of key management time and funds must be well thought when looking at business operations needs. Focus on the future of CRM by using and creating AI in analytics has helped companies like Salesforce, Microsoft, Oracle, and SAP to continuously work together to maintain and develop their products with AI, machine learning, and analytics to better understand and ultimately serve needs of their customers with CRM in mind as shown in the Table 1.

3.3 Marketing Intelligence and Customer Relationship Management

Due to the various changes in connection, context, and business content over the years. Marketing has become a tool capable of responding to the needs of companies to better win over their target audience and learn about their options in the face of competition. The history of marketing began with industrial downsizing, when manufacturing went from small to large-scale, creating needs, values, and options for customers to choose from. (Shimoyama, 2002) States that the vision of the marketing concept within organizations goes beyond the usual in fact it extends to practically every organization, especially all Small and Medium Enterprises directly to the market. He also states that the function of marketing is “simply the intention to understand and serve the market”. Since CRM is a tool that seeks to associate the company’s activities with customer satisfaction, their existence, and satisfaction, whether internal or external, depends on the actions of marketing. According to (Kotler, 2016), the shortest way to define marketing is meeting human and social needs or “meeting needs profitably”. He also emphasizes that artificial intelligence has revolutionized marketing because technology is constantly evolving and plays a key role in transforming many areas, including marketing and entrepreneurship. The two perspectives on the concept of IT and management depend on the disciplinary approach that CRM uses. Thus, CRM uses IT as a mechanism to design applications and software to support marketing, sales, and business service functions. By contrast, CRM uses management to develop and maintain long-term, beneficial customer relationships, using technology when necessary. In this case, there is a reason for SMEs to make use of the exemplary mechanism of a sustainable relationship cycle shown in Figure 2. Customer relations are not just about collecting information, but identifying critical problems for companies in order to satisfy needs and identify new consumers. A Figure 2 represents the information on the relationship cycle that a company incorporates based on Marketing Intelligence and Customer relationship management. Figure 2 begins with step 1 referring to Marketing, this function within any company is aimed at prospecting or attracting new customers. Step 2 is followed by Sales, whose role is to contact leads that fit the customer profile of your target market. Finally, step 3 is the provision of services and support to the end consumer. The marketing information system enables company managers to acquire information from credible sources for the evolution of the marketing environment within the business. Since each marketing register plays an important role in the development and growth of the company, the internal register is responsible for providing results data, but general marketing provides a basis for real events in books, newspapers, or even trade publications.

Figure 1: The Cycle of the relationship
Source: Author’s own elaboration

Nowadays, general marketing has a more substantial dynamic than in the past because it provides the manager with possibility of talking to clients, suppliers, distributors, and other company managers and monitoring online social networks. The value of the relationship increases when companies use CRM in a competitive market where the dynamics of interaction depend on the service provided by the company. It should be remembered that the business relationship between the company and the customer is an association, connection, interaction, and bond between

two or more people and needs to be selected with effective decisions by selecting and identifying appropriate relationship strategies based on customer value. In the past, intelligence has been seen as a fundamental part of a business's growth. The difference in today's internationalized competitive scenario is that it depends on structuring as a fundamental component in order to be part of a more competitive market and, as a result, to be better placed in the market. On the other hand, there are various designations for intelligence used by companies, such as market intelligence, competitive intelligence, creative intelligence, and innovation, environmental intelligence, technology intelligence and organizational intelligence, among others. In general, organizations or companies need to understand that intelligence is a fast and effective process with long-term results because its structuring defines the choice of a market intelligence team. In fact, the choice of team is based on the size of the company, geographical location, organizational structure, business activity, decision-making power and the technology to be used or available.

According to (Pinto, 2020) the creation of an intelligence area in a company means that it acts competitively and adheres to a mandatory management policy, although those that do so are by definition visionary, innovative, and aware, with the capacity and possibility to create competitive advantages in the market. He also states that there are certain factors that need to be changed or modified in the first phase of implementing market intelligence, such as a change in culture, both in the operationalization, sharing, and organization of information and in the institutionalization of corporate governance.

In addition, many companies are afraid of losing their employees or losing the status quo acquired in day-to-day corporate life, but in reality, these changes only increase the company's growth because new information and communication technology tools are implemented with corporate incentive policies. However, these tools are based on electronic document management, virtual communities, intranet, internet, and internet phone and should be used in their entirety, avoiding a lack of functionality or disorganization of information. At the same time, these sophisticated tools cover creativity and innovation (knowledge management) and business intelligence (competitive intelligence).

4. Framework Concept

At this stage, was decided to approach the model created with its implementation, strategy, and development. The adapted approach takes place in a period of technological transformation of CRM with the organizational performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in the food industry. The CRM strategy and implementation model used several insights from the literature made by (Wang, 2004), (Mohamad, 2014), (Pinto, 2020), (Payne A. &, 2005), (Costa, 2020), (Reinartz, 2004), (Chen, 2003), (Parvatiyar, 2001). Many of these studies have an implementation and modification model according to the literature review. In fact, the model created and its implementation depends on the types of CRM models, in this case, the Payne & Frow model. It was therefore possible to identify five elements that are constantly used when creating or recreating a CRM strategy and implementation model. The model used Firstly, there was a major problem in adapting Employee Engagement, Evaluation of CRM Readiness, CRM Change Management, and CRM Project Management and Organizational performance into the model created. The reason behind this problem was the five elements identified in the literature review as it doesn't make sense to introduce elements that don't create a symbiosis. However, it is necessary to distinguish this group of elements from each other as follows: five Core Cross-Functional Process, four Key Implementation Processes, and One Functional Processes.

Given that the goal of any company or organization's strategy is profitability, the functional process was introduced into the model to understand the role of each element when linked to organizational performance. Strategic planning takes place within the context of the organization and the introduction of CRM as a technological tool can help an organization to deliver effective productivity and target customers through the use of customer databases, store data collected from various channels, and improve communication and collaboration with customers.

Figure 2: Organizational performance of the CRM strategy and implementation model

Source: Author's own elaboration

This study represents an organizing model for developing and implementing CRM in the food manufacturing industry which is recursive, the functional process is a management process in that its many activities have to be managed simultaneously and some elements will have to be revised as a result of later activities. Basically, the business model follows a management formula Evolution of CRM readiness + Strategy Development process + Value Creation Process + Multi-Channel Integration Process+ Performance Assessment Process + Data Repository (Warehouse) + Employer Engagement Process + CRM Project Management + CRM Change Management = Organizational Performance based on the limitations and technological needs of the real world. The equation aims to show the real world that CRM practices play a fundamental role in organizational performance. The model that forms a framework of the paper is shown in the Figure 2.

5. Explanation of the Essential Cross-Functional Processes

According to (Li S. W., 2022) the implementation of cross-functional coordination incorporates a series of elements that regulate customer coordination and improve companies' CPIs. He continues by saying that there is a great need for companies to better satisfy customer demands and create value, and the coordination of the company as a whole

facilitating the coordination of customers and also the information processing needs of companies. This part will be explaining the five critical implementation elements of a successful CRM program identified during the interaction research in Figure 2.

5.1 Strategy Development Process

Strategic development is often considered to be strategic planning and it really is a fundamental part of a well-functioning organization. The internal and external changes within the development of a strategy depend very much on the objectives and analysis made by a leader and manager in the company. The development of a strategy allows the organization to have a single focus, proactive thinking, and for investors and leaders to communicate in order to increase revenues and profits, reduce costs, and create opportunities that can benefit the company in terms of products and services against the competition, thus allowing the companies to stay more time in the market.

(Miles, 2003) States that a general model recognized by the adaptive process was developed, this model was called the adaptive cycle. He continues by saying that the general model has the function of strategic choice for the study of organizations and the use of ideas formulated by theorists as a model for the expansion of organizations. He also emphasizes in this regard that the strategic choice argues that external factors such as the environment and internal factors such as the choice of top managers are critical determinants of organizational structure and process.

(Dyson, 2007) Claims that strategy-making is a whole set of exploratory and deliberate actions to shape the future of an organization. He also claims based on animations that all the implications made need a sense of direction, even if there is no explicit sense of direction. Basically, strategy is seen within many organizations as a coherent set of discrete individual actions belonging to an objective and at the same time supported by a self-sustaining critical mass portfolio of desperate competition.

The vote for desired business direction within an organization is seen as a starting engine for strategic development and then as a vision and mission for goals to be achieved within the organization. Thus, can also be declared that a well-articulated direction will provide behaviors and responses that quickly change the direction desired during the strategic development. Acting socio-psychologically, there is a whole institutionalized socialization process to transform socialization into a socially incorporated relationship with norms and values beyond the command of the founders, creating a lasting and valued relationship within the organization. The formal and informal processes of negotiation, commitment, and execution mean that institutions have an evident relationship between three basic interactions.

(Ring, 1994) Declared that the informal and informal processes of negotiation, commitment, and execution mean that institution have an evident relationship of three basic interactions: a) there is a mass replacement of formal legal contracts for psychological contracts. b) Relationships or agreements made between known people in the business sector result in informal role relationship. c) All business mandates made by the initial contracting agents depends on an estimated time to be fulfilled, otherwise there is a great possibility of corruption between formal and informal commitments and understandings.

5.2 Value Creation Process

Value creation has several definitions, including a business strategy with a fundamental approach intended to direct organizations and define the commercial purpose. In any sector of the company, the innovative thinking of converting commitment and understanding of deep situations from meetings to decision-making depends largely on daily interests or decision-making in meetings in which discussion guides business and creates digital platforms to improve the system of business. In digital strategy and execution, companies do not only rely on innovative or emerging technologies to better serve customers, the use of business innovation plays a fundamental role as a cornerstone of the business in the creation of value. Business success is at the heart of creating value with customers. In economic domains, value creation requires transforming resources into something valuable for the company using hard work, that is, each employee is part of the whole, and so if an employee has a problem, the company also has one. Therefore, it is important to highlight that the essence of value creation is linked to sustainability, communities, environment, products and services, and above all enabling stronger relationships with customers. At this level, it is certainly necessary to say that companies need to innovate in response to changing market conditions, streamline operations, refine products, and promote a culture of excellence.

According to (Prahalad, 2004) companies have shown a paradigm shift in business when talking about consumers, the companies can no longer design products, develop production processes, craft marketing messages, and control

sales channels without customer data. He also states that there is a conventional market relationship in which companies and consumers play the same role in the value-creation process. A long and lasting relationship with a company is likely to create value from a good understanding of its needs and in turn enables the company to control future competition focused on an individual-centered co-creation of value using mechanisms such as the six pillars of Customer Experience Excellence (CEE).

(Amit, 2001) States that any transaction made in e-business is denoted as value as long as it creates total value. He also emphasizes that a value created can come from any element such as firms, customers, or even any other element part of the transaction. He continues by saying that exists four major value drivers that were identified in his analysis efficiency, complementarities, lack-in, novelty, and the linkages among them that create a total value creation. Value creation has a significant impact on business understanding and importance. This understanding and importance can be seen in various forms of action and decisive factors in the construction and success of a company, including customer satisfaction, loyalty, and maintaining a competitive advantage. The value proposition also brings with it advantages, whether explicit or implicit of specific value creation packages. The packages have fundamental sources of value for the customer such as competitive pricing, product or service innovation, and customizes solutions capable of adapting the offer to the needs of individual customers.

5.3 Multi-Channel Integration Process

SME organizations are facing challenges and changes related to customers, markets, and marketing initiatives. Thus, there is a need for intervention to improve this process of interaction with customers through various channels, whether indirect or direct adopting the definition of multichannel interaction. With the improvement of this customer intervention channel, consumers will have more control over their purchasing power, satisfaction, and familiarity with the seller, product and service. However, the development of SME organizations must be continuous and effective, involving traditional marketing techniques because the use of cross-channels facilitates a better customer experience than a single channel. One of the best initiatives to use the multichannel channel for SME organizations is the use of digital technologies. Actually, the use of digital technologies enables organizations SMEs to adopt new business models, organization designs, strategies, and work practices to gain a competitive advantage. The model in the figure understands what organizations need to employ now and will need to integrate in the future. The use of mechanisms such as CRM to manage customer relationships following all these changes in the market, technology, and know-how of how to do business makes it possible and will make it possible to better understand who the customer is, what are they needs and wants and which channels are preferred for contacting consumption and purchase as shown in the figure. The storage of information by SME organizations is important due to the benefits it provides to the marketing development strategy to reach the target group with the right message, advertisement, product, or service shown in the Figure 2.

(Avşar, 2021) States that technological advancement in recent years has brought advantages in terms of payments, especially for the Supply Chain Industry, where payment techniques such as mobile wallets, P2P, and mobile payments are being used by major players such as Amazon, Paypal, Apple, and Facebook. She also expresses the idea that the Omni-Channel strategy is used when the multi-channel strategy does not work in some sectors.

(Wilson, 2007) States that the organization needs methods and programs that can bring excellent results to the marketing sector. He continues by saying that these results are aimed at the change of channels from the traditional one to the more developed one, bringing competitive challenges for the creation of a new map structure focused on; industry strategy, positioning of the organization, and refining the product/service offered. These potential changes in SMEs are called disintermediation or reinter-mediation, and their integration is considered a big risk of intuitive bet called innovative thinking implemented by many SMEs in the planning process.

(Goersch, 2002) Emphasizes that many companies nowadays have decided to start with a business separation, moving away from the traditional era and opting for the technological era using internet operations management. He also mentions that after the influence of this thinking around the internet, many retailers began to recognize multichannel integration as the preferred strategy because it allows synergies between channels which in turn benefits customers by improving the way they acquire, extend, and retain customers from retailers, despite the fact that multichannel integration brings with it advantages that outweigh the benefits of channel separation and the difficulties in channel integration.

(Verhoef, 2015) States in his research that the impact of channels on performance has caused an availability effect by using a multi-channel integration process. He points out the impact of opening an offline store on the performance of a retailer with existing online and catalog channels, the result concluded that the retailer had more positive results increasing returns and exchanges, and having higher overall revenues with more purchase frequency across channels.

(Hossain, 2019) States that the only form that a company has to excel in competition is by maintaining or providing a quality service to its customers due to factors like long-term sustainable profitability in a service landscape. He also mentions that the perceived service quality can be understood by different studies and practically used by organizations SME to compare the expectations of services provided by the company with what is exactly the type of service performance received by the customers

(Osterlund, 2005) Demonstrates in his research that channel mix and channel integration should be approached differently, in the sense that channel mix must be acknowledged by its capacity to use different channels and each one being viewed independently of the other, on the other hand, channel integration is defined as a mechanism that uses multiple channels with different functions within a single sales process. He also points out the fact that channel integration brings up questions that SME organizations have been trying to answer continuously in terms of management, how to divide workers into different sectors into distinct tasks and then achieve coordination and better productivity among them.

5.4 Performance Assessment Process

The performance Assessment process conditions a whole series of aspects that can help SME organizations focus on the performance of each employee. This performance can be demonstrated through motivation and retention rates, as well as by keeping them closer to the company's mission, creating a better working environment and a stronger organization, while also being able to help identify and develop future leaders. However, making performance assessment part of the culture can help organizations boost their performance and meet challenges with senior managers and line managers. Necessarily, it is very difficult for startups and Small and Medium Enterprises as a whole to have the monetary capacity capable of training a line of managers to conduct meaningful performance assessments. In fact, a well-trained manager is capable of presenting results and giving positive and effective responses to transformations that arise inside and outside the business environment in which the company operates, making priority in the face of pressing front-line duties. (Messick, 1994) States that it is possible to find contrasts between performances and products when analyzing structured and unstructured problems related to the involvement of workers and line managers so that the company has an effective process. He points out that a company should focus more on increasing the level of satisfaction of all line managers, rather than getting a CEO on board because it will help understand, how to access talent, reinforce performance, how to do performance coaching and how to engage employees.

According to (Van Looy, 2016) position time, cost, quality and flexibility as the common aspects of business process performance measurement. He also points out that there are different models for analyzing performance, including the tree of objectives and performance indicators, which presents five perspectives of process performance: The financial perspective, the customer perspective, the employee perspective, the society perspective and the innovation perspective.

(Engelhard, 1996) States that educated people cannot unlearn in his research Evaluating rater accuracy in performance assessments. He also points out that educational and psychological assessments are based on classification data made by one or more professionals within the field of expertise, however, there is another way of evaluating professionals in the educational field which is the evaluation judgment using a rating scale, on the other hand, the psychological side is based on performance appraisal.

(Van Raan, 2014) States in his work on analysis for evaluating research performance and scientific mapping that the more citations, bibliography, and common references an article has, the stronger its relationship with the bibliographic coupling strength. He also points out that the strength of co-citation is only greater if a pair of articles cite more articles. Contrary to what the author highlighted when looking at the context of the performance evaluation process, the more positive feedback a manager receives from group members within any organization, the more evident his or her success inside and outside the work environment. (Gravina, 2021) Affirms that organizations have only three levels of characteristics to be evaluated: the organization level, the process level, and the performer level. He agreed that for there to be large-scale organizational change the company needs to support the process

levels, in addition, the performance level cannot be dismissed due to the fact that it is a mechanism that drives processes and organizational changes.

5.5 Data Repository (Warehouse)

With technological evolution and the continued growth of globalization, elements such as artificial intelligence (AI), automation, analytics, and AI reality software have had a major impact on SME organizations. With the emergence of the data warehouse or enterprise data (EDW) it was possible to create a single, central, and consistent system for obtaining data from a multi-channel system with a performance assessment to support data analysis, data mining, intelligence artificial intelligence (AI), and finally machine learning. There has been a whole process of conditioning SME organizations, especially in the food manufacturing sector in terms of business intelligence (BI) solutions for more than three decades, the use of data warehousing system enables the maneuvering of new types of data and hosting them into a database.

(Langley, 1999) Underlines that is difficult to collect qualitative process data in organizations as it is different to isolate units of analysis in an unambiguous way. He also points out that researchers struggle to differentiate a change from the decision about what strategy should be adopted.

(Rothwell, 1994) articulates that some strategies established during the 1980s in technological process innovation continue to lead SME organizations of the food manufacturing industry to remain committed to technological accumulation (technology strategy); strategic networking and speed to market (time-based strategy). He also emphasizes that SME organizations are constantly challenging each other to gain market competition towards increasingly better-integrated products and manufacturing strategies (design for manufacturability). The data warehouse architecture is an element built around a relational database system, local or in the cloud, where they will be stored and processed. The data warehouse architecture is an element built around a relational database system, local or in the cloud, where they will be stored and processed.

(Ariyachandra, 2006) says that there are four main components such as central database, ETL tool, metadata, and access tools, moreover, it is necessary that these elements are fast, to analyze and obtain data in real-time. He emphasizes his research of architectures over time by explaining that architecture data's intended purpose is based on terms of information, system unity, organizational impact, and people. However, taking into account the explanation of the organizational, technological, and people metadata has become an important system with reports, panels, and SQL (structured query language).

6. Explanation of the Key Implementation Process

(Nah, 2001) Articulates that companies today need initiatives that can improve their anticipation, response, and reaction to growing market demands or simply disappear. He argues that implementation is more than a document as it constitutes steps that move any organizational team toward a defined goal or necessary initiative. That's the reason why this part will be explaining the four critical implementation elements of a successful CRM program identified during the interaction research in the Figure 2.

6.1 Evaluation of CRM readiness

The CRM readiness assessment is a mechanism for reading the elements of CRM in a given model chosen after its implementation. This mechanism aims to show directors, managers, and associates the development of their organization concerning its competitors. (Kim, 2003) Argues in his research for the evaluation of CRM effectiveness that the implementation of CRM requires a return on investment in itself and its cost depends on the tools to be used, in this case, there is difficulty in finding elements of evaluation as tangible or intangible. He points out that the only way to solve this evaluation problem is by adopting multi-criteria methods such as information economics, cost-benefits analysis (CBA) returns on management (ROM), value analysis, and investment portfolios.

(Ocker, 2003) States in his research that the developed theoretical model of CRM readiness is divided into three dimensions of alignment; intellectual, social, and technological. He states that the model was built to create more business value, both within the organization and outside it, believing that female workers are equal to make workers, they think the same and act in the same way and will use you in the same way as men workers by aligning to complementary factors.

(Najafi, 2015) Argues that prevent the risk of failure rate of the CRM readiness assessment at the pre-implementation phase and better understand its implementation process, there are few studies carried out. He continues by saying that CRM readiness assessment is referred to by researchers as a common factor called readiness criteria to be able to measure the level of organizational readiness.

The readiness audit can provide an initial overview of the main CRM priorities to be able to understand the importance and priorities of all the effort necessary to apply. Companies within SME that have growth and development outside of common sense can apply a more comprehensive CRM audit, taking into account that our model demonstrates this possibility.

6.2 CRM Change Management

CRM change handling is seen through transitions from an old system to a new CRM system. These changes come with people management so a collective commitment is made to provide a functional capacity capable of dealing with any adversity that the system may have. The reason why CRM change management is used in Figure 2 focuses on the perspective that behind these adversities of change, relationship management with customers or end users, uncertainties and fears play a dominant role in the alternative CRM system that cannot provide adequate answers regarding its implementation, demanding the entire corporate culture.

(Iriana, 2006) Develops some CRM change management practices based on strategic organization and employee involvement that are seen as activities for the operation. He also mentions some recommended change models focused on Kotler's eight stages and a change framework like the Seven S's.

(Rababah, 2011) Emphasize that his CRM process model which is quite similar to Figure 2 illustrates that CRM change management focuses on market intelligence and in turn strengthens all types of customer relationships and their productivity interaction between buyer and seller which could combine with the exchange of products and services for money, information exchange, or social exchange.

(Roberts, 2005) Reorients changes in operations, highlighting that many of these changes are fundamental for the company processes and can only be changed by requiring time and expense for process reengineering but not essentially operational. He also carefully points out that CRM brings with it long-term organizational change and development and its failure depends on its implementation.

6.3 CRM Project Management

Understanding how CRM for Project Management works can help any SME organization in the food sector Industry create a platform to unify customer data to understand their demands regarding the cost of services or products, quality, discounts, and the level of satisfaction. The Figure 2 demonstrates that with every move made to expand CRM initiatives, there is a need for effective project management because projects that exceed budgets and deadlines create damage to the company's CRM and ROI.

(Beldi, 2010) Recommends CRM functionalities and the implementation of organizational change, so that the company-client hierarchy structure together with the CRM project team to make use of all CRM extensions, Figure 2.

(Bull, 2003) Identify in your CRM case study that one of the main problems in project implementation is choosing an efficient team to provide immediate responses to problems and the resolution or presentation of projects within a deadline. He also shows that once the company compromises its project team, automatically it compromises the target customers, causing the company to have additional costs by configuring the software, changing business processes, and disrupting the organizational performance of the SME. First of all, it is necessary to evaluate the company's sector of activity before implementing the CRM model due to the variety of projects and the company's length of stay in the market. In the same way can happen with CRM as organizations can adopt to implement operational CRM, analytical CRM or collaborative CRM depending on its projects as well.

6.4 Employee Engagement

Humans are all animals and the rules that govern the lines of lions or wolves of our closest relatives. The primates are no different than the rules that govern human lives due to the constant competition with each other, competition for bread, to eat, to seek water and shelter. Besides, only man can survive without a tribe.

(Albrecht, 2015) States that after so many studies carried out in the academic field on the involvement of employees within SME organization, its definition incorporates vigor, dedication and absorption that every worker must have

towards their work. He also defined employer engagement in a more comprehensive standard way, focusing on the level of achievement that each person should have in their work using all available learning resources, and physical, cognitive, and emotional strength to counter adversities that may arise. Engaged employees have a particularity that separates them from disengaged employees. This particularity is based on clear connections, job satisfaction, employee morale, and above all, communication. Communication is considered a peaceful element for resolving conflicts or problems, it means that all employees are engaged in maintaining the company's involvement, values, and objectives. According to (Anitha, 2014) company employees are often characterized by committed, non-committed, and actively demobilized employees. He points out that of all employees, those who are actively demobilized are considered the most dangerous, in addition to compromising the work of others and destroying the company's performance. Furthermore, since 1990, employee involvement has been considered a management theory and a weapon to combat competition, because it has extreme links with the profitability and financial health of a company. (Saks, 2014) Emphasizes the psychology of employee engagement by saying that psychological significance is a feeling of return of investment remunerated in physical energy currency, that is, the more valuable and useful workers feel within their companies, the greater their dedication will be. (Macey, 2008) Explains in engagement as extra-role behavior that the success of a worker is the success of a company and that changing any worker's behavior is a mere adaptation to the success-constructive communication of the same company.

7. Explanation of the Functional Process

Functional process is very focused on hierarchies and its sequence of actions aims to bring the desired outcome and customer satisfaction. (Davenport, 1990) States that companies have two primary reasons to understand and measure existing processes before re-designing them, the first is based on the failure to understand the existing process so that it does not get repeated, and the second is based on future improvements. He also points out that many organizations should redesign business processes by using IT five steps; develop business vision and process objectives, identify critical or bottleneck processes, identify current problems and set the baseline, brainstorm new process approaches, and implement organizational and technical aspects. That's the reason why this part will be explaining the critical implementation element of a successful CRM program identified during the interaction research in Figure 2.

7.1 Organizational Performance

Wisdom leads a person to have actions and purity of inner light to follow a desired path. For this reason, it is necessary to evaluate organizational performance to help Small and Medium Enterprises to identify areas of improvement opportunities and provide insights into the capabilities and skills of current employees. By looking at Figure 2, there was a need to set up a model that its implementation can help SME organizations justify the use of capital and identify problems in areas of managerial decision-making

(Barros, 2014) In his study considered quality performance as an indicator to measure company performance and, as a result a strong positive correlation between the two variables was found. He also highlights that the objective is to understand two different sectors, the manufacturing industry and services, and what kind of impact this has on Portuguese performance organizations.

(Li S. R.-N.-N., 2006) Indicates that organizational performance has short-term and long-term objectives, the short-term is based on increasing productivity and reducing inventory and cycle time, on the other hand, the long-term refers to an increase in profits and the participation of suppliers as members within the market.

(Delaney, 1996) By using different hypotheses, the author states that progressive HRM practices are positively correlated to organizational performance. He also mentions that as a second hypothesis synergies among progressive HRM practices are positively correlated to organizational performance. (Samson, 1999) Focusing in his research limitations about total quality management (TQM) by using a cross sectional study he found that elements of TQM, leadership, people management and customer focus have a significantly positive effect. He also mentions that the reason behind the use of TQM elements is based on the idea concerning the design and introduction of products and services as well as the focus on integrated production, delivery requirements, and supplier performance management.

8. Conclusion

Over a long period of Customer Relationship Management evolution, companies have adopted an organizational mechanism for understanding the effects of marketing intelligence and practices for maintaining long-term relationships with current consumers and building relationships with new consumers. Before the Industrial Revolution, small and medium-sized enterprises often knew their customers by name and occupation but were often unaware of the value base of the customer based on acquisition, recovery, and retention. The customers are the basis of an organization's success. In other words, if the customer has a problem, the company has a problem, so the company must invest in long-term strategic development. In this article, strategic development incorporates an understanding of the CRM strategy and its implementation. First of all, we start by understanding that CRM is an element that supports the transformation of companies that intend to implement long-term models based on strategy, practice, and well-defined technology. Furthermore, its implementation requires knowledge of its scale to be able to manage customers in the short and long term. Its dimension starts with operational CRM, analytical CRM, and finally collaborative CRM. Secondly, CRM has a close relationship with marketing intelligence, sales, and services, thus creating a cycle of relationships between departments to support the end consumer and, in turn, the company. Marketing Intelligence brings significant advantages to the company, such as acquiring information from credible sources, competitive advantage, competitive intelligence, creative intelligence and innovation, environmental intelligence, technological intelligence, and organizational intelligence. As a final part, the research was based on organizational performance in SMEs in the food industry, since studies in this field are scarce and there is a greater likelihood, according to the literature review of having the greatest positive impact. In addition, this model of CRM strategy and implementation was identified in many studies of the literature review, but without many similarities with the model in this research. The CRM model in this research opted for similarity based on Payne & Frow's model, making it possible to formulate a management formula in which the objective is to understand how these elements can create development and growth in the organization's performance. The purpose of the inclusion of the elements chosen by the research was the symbiosis of these elements since any element that failed to create symbiosis using the literature review would not be accepted by the model. The research decided to divide the model into five central cross-functional processes whose aim is to regulate customer interaction and improve companies' CPIs. Another division is the four-key implementation process, the aim of which is to help companies anticipate, respond, and react to growing market demands or simply disappear. As last, we have the functional processes whose aim is to focus on hierarchies and provide the desired customer satisfaction. To conclude, the model has proved useful in identifying and providing solutions for the organizational performance of SMEs in the Food Manufacturing Industry. Because the encounter process is focused on good communication and involves interactions and transactions between the customers and the suppliers, as can also be necessary for building customer experience while others may be more focus oriented towards value co-creation (Payne A. F., 2008).

References

- Albrecht, S. L. (2015). Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage: An integrated approach. *Journal of organizational effectiveness: People and performance*, Vol 2.1, pp. 7-35.
- Amit, R. &. (2001). Value Creation in E-business. *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol 22, pp. 493–520.
- Anitha, J. (2014). Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol 63, pp. 308-323.
- Ariyachandra, T. &. (2006). Which data warehouse architecture is most successful? *Business Intelligence*, Vol 11, pp. 1-4.
- Atnafu, D. &. (2018). The impact of inventory management practice on firms' competitiveness and organizational performance: Empirical evidence from micro and small enterprises in Ethiopia. *Cogent Business & Management*, Vol 5, pp. 1-16.
- Avşar, B. (2021). Omni-Channel Trends in Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal of International Trade*, Vol 7, pp. 97-104.
- Aziz, N. A. (2010). How Will Market Orientation and External Environment Influence the Performance among SMEs in the Agro-Food Sector in Malaysia? *International Business Research*, Vol 3, pp. 154-164.

- Barros, S. A. (2014). The Relationship between Quality Approaches and Their Impact on Portuguese Companies' Quality Performance. *International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management* (pp. pp. 7–9). Bali [online]: <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/handle/1822/36272> (accessed 07 December 2023).
- Beldi, A. &. (2010). Managing customer relationship management projects: The case of a large French telecommunications company. *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol 28, pp. 339–351.
- Bull, C. (2003). Strategic Issues in Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Implementation. *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol 9, pp. 592-602.
- Caldari, K. (2007). Alfred Marshall's critical analysis of scientific management. *The European Journal of the History of Economic Thought*, Vol 14, pp. 55-78.
- Chen, I. J. (2003). Understanding customer relationship management (CRM) People, process and technology. *Business Process Management*, Vol 9, pp. 672-688.
- Costa, L. M. (2020). Competitive Management and Application of Customer Relationship Management. *Revista Ipanec*, Vol 1, pp. 134-156.
- Da Silva Pinto, E. C. (2020). Marketing Intelligence and Customer Relationship Management - A Quantitative Study. *Associação Brasileira*, pp. 16-31.
- Da Silva, R. P. (2020). O efeito da implementação dos sistemas ERP e CRM na satisfação dos clientes. *Revista Científica Hermes*, Vol 27, pp. 184-207.
- Davenport, T. H. (1990). The new industrial engineering: information technology and business process redesign. *Sloan Management Review*, Vol 31, pp. 11-27.
- Delaney, J. T. (1996). The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Perceptions of Organizational Performance. *Academy of Management journal*, Vol 39, pp. 949-969.
- Drucker, P. F. (1977). *People and performance: The best of Peter Drucker*. New York, NY: Management. Harper's College Press.
- Dyche, J. (2002). *The CRM Handbook: A Business Guide to Customer Relationship Management*. New York, NY: Addison-Wesley Professional.
- Dyson, R. G. (2007). The strategic development process. *Supporting strategy: Frameworks, methods and models*, pp. 3-24.
- Engelhard, G. (1996). Evaluating Rater Accuracy in Performance Assessments. *Journal of Educational Measurement*, Vol 33, pp. 56-70.
- Espinosa-Gracia, A. &-C. (2023). Long waves, paradigm shifts, and income distribution, 1929–2010 and afterwards. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, Vol 33, pp. 1365-1396.
- Gholami, M. H.-S. (2013). Investigating the influence of knowledge management practices on organizational performance: an empirical study. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, Vol 10, pp. 205-216.
- Goersch, D. (2002). Multi-Channel Integration and Its Implementation for Retail Web Sites. *ECIS 2002 Proceedings*, Vol 11, pp. 6-8.
- Gravina, N. N. (2021). Assessment of employee performance. *Journal of Organizational Behavior Management*, Vol 41.2, pp. 124-149.
- Hossain, T. M. (2019). Multichannel integration quality: A systematic review and agenda for future research. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol 49, pp. 154-163.
- Iriana, R. &. (2006). Customer relationship management (CRM): system implementations. *International Journal of Knowledge, Culture and Change Management*, Vol 6, pp. 1-15.
- Kim, J. S. (2003). A model for evaluating the effectiveness of CRM using the balanced scorecard. *Journal of interactive Marketing*, Vol 17, pp. 5-19.
- Kotler. (2016). *Marketing Management*. Harlow: British Library Cataloguing.
- Kracklauer, A. H. (2004). *Collaborative Customer Relationship Management: Taking CRM to the Next Level*. Boston: Springer Science & Business Media.
- Langley, A. (1999). Strategies for theorizing from process data. *Academy of Management Review*, Vol 24, pp. 691-710.
- Li, S. R.-N.-N. (2006). The impact of supply chain management practices on competitive advantage and organizational performance. *Omega*, Vol 34, pp. 107-124.

- Li, S. W. (2022). The impact of cross-functional coordination on customer coordination and operational performance: an information processing view. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol 122, pp. 167-193.
- Macey, W. H. (2008). The meaning of employee engagement. *Industrial and organizational Psychology*, Vol 1, pp. 3-30.
- Maria, S. (2019). Cooperative Business Development: The Principality Challenge. *Revista de Gestão e Organizações Cooperativas*, Vol 6, pp. 1-18.
- Mbugi, I. O. (2022). Effects of inventory control management systems on organization performance in Tanzania manufacturing industry-A case study of food and beverage manufacturing company in Mwanza city. *International journal of Engineering, Business and Management*, pp. 2-6.
- Messick, S. (1994). The interplay of evidence and consequences in the validation of performance assessments. *Educational researcher*, Vol 23, pp. 13-23.
- Miles, R. E. (2003). Organizational Strategy, Structure, and Process. *Academy of management review*, Vol 3, pp. 546-562.
- Mohamad, S. H. (2014). Customer relationship management practices: The impact on organizational performance in SMEs of food manufacturing industry. *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol 13, pp. 35-48.
- Murakami, Y. &. (1996). An anticlassical political-economic analysis: A vision for the next century. California: Stanford University Press.
- Murta, S. R. (2017). CRM como ferramenta de análise de dados: um estudo de caso. *Revista Petra*, Vol 3, pp. 10-15.
- Nah, F. F.-H.-S. (2001). Critical factors for successful implementation of enterprise systems. *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol 7, pp. 285-296.
- Najafi, E. S.-N. (2015). Decision Making Methodology for CRM Readiness Assessment. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering*. Tehran: Research Gate.
- Ocker, R. J. (2003). Assessing the Readiness of Firms for CRM: A Literature Review and Research Model. Paper presented at the System Sciences, 2003. *Proceeding of the 36th Annual Hawaii International Conference on*.
- Osterlund, D. W. (2005). Channel integration: an organisational perspective. *International Journal of Financial Services Management*, Vol 1.1, pp. 26-40.
- Ostrovitianov. (1972). *Manual de Economia Política*. Lisboa: Editorial Estampa, Lda.
- Parvatiyar, A. &. (2001). Customer Relationship Management: Emerging Practice, Process, and Discipline. *Journal of Economic and Social Research*, Vol 3, pp. 1-34.
- Payne, A. &. (2005). A strategic framework for customer relationship management. *Journal of marketing*, Vol 69, pp. 167-176.
- Payne, A. &. (2016). Customer relationship management: Strategy and implementation. In *The Marketing Book*. Routledge, Vol 69, pp. 439-466.
- Payne, A. F. (2008). Managing the co-creation of value. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, Vol 36, pp. 83-96.
- Peter. (2011). *Management: Tasks, Responsibilities, Practices*. New York: Routledge.
- Pinto, d. S. (2020). Marketing Intelligence and Customer Relationship Management - A Quantitative Study. *Associação Brasileira de Empresas de Pesquisa (ABEP)*, Vol 13, pp. 16-31.
- Prahalad, C. K. (2004). Co-creating unique value with customers. *Strategy & leadership*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol 32, pp. 4-9.
- Rababah, K. M. (2011). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Processes from Theory to Practice: The Pre-implementation Plan of CRM System. *International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning*, Vol 1, pp. 22-27.
- Rangone, A. B. (2002). A framework to support the formulation of internet strategy in traditional enterprises. *International Journal of Business Performance Management*, Vol 4, pp. 248-278.
- Reinartz, W. K. (2004). The customer relationship management process: Its measurement and impact on performance. *Journal of marketing research*, Vol 41, pp. 293-305.
- Ring, P. S. (1994). Developmental processes of cooperative interorganizational relationships. *Academy of management review*, Vol 19, pp. 90-118.
- Roberts, M. L. (2005). Strategy, technology and organisational alignment: Key components of CRM success. *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, pp. 315-326.

- Rothwell, R. (1994). Towards the Fifth-generation Innovation Process. *International Marketing Review*, Vol 11, pp. 7-31.
- Saks, A. M. (2014). What Do We Really Know About Employee Engagement? *Human resource development quarterly*, Vol 25, pp. 155-182.
- Samson, D. &. (1999). The relationship between total quality management practices and operational performance. *Journal of operations management*, Vol 17, pp. 393-409.
- Shimoyama, C. &. (2002). *Administração de Marketing*. Marketing, pp. 3-8.
- Uwe. (2021). *B2B Marketing: A Guidebook for the Classroom to the Boardroom*. Springer International Publishing.
- Van Looy, A. &. (2016). Business process performance measurement: a structured literature review of indicators, measures and metrics. *SpringerPlus*, Vol 5, pp. 1-24.
- Van Raan, A. (2014). Advances in bibliometric analysis: Research performance assessment and science mapping. *Human resource development quarterly*, Vol 87, pp. 17-28.
- Verhoef, P. C. (2015). From multi-channel retailing to omni-channel retailing: introduction to the special issue on multi-channel retailing. *Journal of retailing*, Vol 91, pp. 174-181.
- Visser, M. S. (2019). *Digital marketing fundamentals: From strategy to ROI*. Routledge.
- Wang, Y. P. (2004). An integrated framework for customer value and customer-relationship-management performance: a customer-based perspective from China. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, Vol 14, pp. 169-182.
- Wilson, H. a. (2007). The multi-channel challenge: A dynamic capability approach. *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol 36, pp. 10-20.